

A Guiding Program to Develop Political Efficiency for University Students

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Abstract

The present study aims at testing the effectiveness of the suggested guiding program to develop political efficiency for university students. The descriptive study sample was formed of (130) students from faculty of education, Tanta University, whereas the experimental study sample included (10) students. Also, a subsequent and previous measure was done. The study tools were a measure of political efficiency and suggested guiding program prepared by the researcher. The study findings showed differences with statistical significance among arithmetic means of the experimental group grades in the previous and subsequent measure related to political efficiency in favor of the subsequent measure. Meanwhile, the subsequent measure of political efficiency witnessed no differences with statistical significance in the arithmetic means of the experimental group grades.

Keywords: *Guiding programs, political efficiency, university students*

Introduction

To Individuals see political efficiency as their assistant in changing the injustice political systems and rather building new democratic political ones which respect humans and guarantee all their rights. That concept helps greatly in occurring the political and social change in the world beside making persons able to participate in elections, government and demonstrations, (Saleh 2007). (George, 1974) defined political efficiency as the individual's ability to understand that his/her political participation is effective and the social and political change is possible beside knowing that he or she plays an important role in doing that change. Lee, 2005 argues that political efficiency is a two-dimension concept containing interior and exterior efficiency. The interior efficiency refers to people's beliefs concerning their individual abilities to understand politics. Meanwhile, the exterior efficiency refers to people's beliefs concerning the government response. To illustrate, there is a big difference between political efficiency and political participation. As for the political efficiency, it is a term used for expressing the individual's ability to participate and affect the political system which is formed of two distinctive elements: interior political efficiency and exterior one (Yeich & Levine, 1994). Whereas the political participation means the citizen's right in doing a particular role in making political decision by all legal ways and

monitoring them after being issued by the ruler, (Mashty 2010). In addition, political efficiency is considered a dynamic and progressing process to which persons experience during all life stages. It is also a must for making the individual active and positive in political work inside his/her community, (Gomaa 1984). (Levin, 1991) sees that educational organizations are sources for political efficiency. He adds that learning and curriculum studied by students inside schools and universities which deal with social and political issues is of a great importance because they help students to build their values and attitudes towards problems and issues of their societies. (Abou Hashish & Kamel, 2014) confirm that organizations of social upbringing play an important role in developing political efficiency for university students. Study results showed that the faculty atmosphere contributes in reaching to high levels of political efficiency via reinforcing social and political identity for university students. Lee, 2006 agreed with the previous results, whereas his study aimed at knowing the relationship between 3 types of using the internet: information, entertainment and interactive communications. His study also tried to know the relationship between the two types of efficiency: interior and exterior for American university students. Lee's study also aimed at recognizing the relationship between social identity and political efficiency. Also, it aimed at

predicting political participation for students of nursing faculty after 25th revolution in(2011) in Egypt.

Methodology

In the recent study, the researcher tries to design a multi-technical guiding program to help to develop political efficiency for university students. The study included students from Tanta University representing general frame of the society from which a lot of students from faculty of education were chosen to form the study sample. After reading the previous researches in that field , the program was formed from the guiding aim ,procedural aims of the program , the need to the program , steps of guiding program , mechanism , techniques used in the program, services offered by the program and executive procedures for every and each stage in the program . A political efficiency measure was used in that program which is considered a tool to evaluate the interior and exterior political efficiency for individuals. The measure contains (17) phrases to evaluate the 2 dimensions of political efficiency. There were (9) phrases to measure the exterior efficiency and (8) ones to measure the interior efficiency. Responses were evaluated on a quintuple scale starting with grade 1 (agree) and ending with grade(5) (disagree) according to the phrase direction. Reliability of the measure was tested via agreement percentage of a group of ten specialists in psychology and psychological health. Most phrases were agreed on with a percentage exceeding 80% . Some phrases were amended according to specialists' opinions. Interior harmony of the measure items was verified. To illustrate, values of correlation coefficients (N=105) rated from (0, 73) to (0, 87). All correlation coefficients of the items had significance at level of(0,01). An (SPSS) program was used to get the study results by using Pearson correlation coefficients to know the relationship between the study variables. Also, Wilcoxon test was used in the research to show the significance and differences between arithmetic means of grades of the previous and subsequent measures in a hand and the subsequent and following up measures in another hand.

Result

After verifying methodology and validity of the premise, there were differences with statistical significance between arithmetic means of the experimental group grades in the previous and subsequently measure on the scale of the political efficiency (interior, exterior and total degree) at the side of the subsequently measure because of using the practical program and using the researcher to Wilcoxon test to measure the differences between means of measure degrees for related samples of the previous and subsequently measure as the(Table. 1) shows

Table 1. differences between means of measure degrees for related samples

Dimensions	Measures	Arithmetic Mean	Means of negative grades	Means of positive grades	Z value	Significance level
Interior efficiency	pre	10	,00	5,50	2,820	,005
	post	42,3				
Exterior efficiency	pre	9,5	,00	5,50	2,818	,005
	post	37,8				
Total grade	pre	19,5	,00	5,50	2,820	,005
	post	80,1				

Table (1) shows differences with statistical significance between means of measure grades (pre and post) for the benefit of the post measure in the political efficiency dimensions. (Z) Value was (2,820) for the interior efficiency, 2,818 for the exterior one and (2,820) for the total grade. That means that zero premises is not accepted, whereas the alternative one is accepted, so we conclude that the guiding program is effective.

Discussion

Pre results show that the guiding program has an effect on the political efficiency because of the use of good ways and techniques which were proven to be effective in a lot of studies and researches. Focusing on the cognitive variables, the guiding program tried to change some beliefs and thoughts or at least to amend deviant behaviors and replacing them with correct ones which lead to making cognitive and conductive changes for the study sample. Depending on psychological learning sessions, the guiding program tried to increase students' awareness of the political efficiency concept, push them to participate and to warn against wrong concepts. Also, the guiding program helped students to shoulder their responsibility and respect others' rights and duties.

Conclusion

Political efficiency is essential to help individuals participate in political life; the thing which leads to making interaction with the surrounding environment and drawing its dimensions to make it proper. Students in universities are considered suitable persons for practicing political efficiency due to their psychological and emotional growth in addition to having good abilities to do so, so they should be treated as an effective factor in any society.

Recommendations

The entire document should be in times New Roman font size 10. Paper title must be centered, bold, regular font size 20 and all with upper case. Author names must

be centered, bold, regular font size 10 . Author affiliation must be regular font size 9. Email address must be centered, italic, font size 9. Recommended font sizes are shown in Table 1. No more than 3 levels of headings should be used. Level 1 heading must be left-justified, bold, regular font size 14 and numbered using Arabic numerals. Level 2 headings must be left-justified, bold, regular font size 12 and numbered as sub-heading (i.e 1.1). Level 3 heading must be left-justified, bold, italic font size 10 and numbered as sub-sub heading (i.e 1.1.1) and the first letter of each word capitalized.

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